

EXPLORING THE CONCEPT OF VISHADA AND ITS HEALING THROUGH SATVAVAJAYA CHIKITSA.- REVIEW ARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

The fundamental meaning of health according to the classics of Ayurveda draws attention to the interaction between *Manas* and *Shareera*. समदोषः समाग्निश्च समधातुमलक्रियः । प्रसन्नात्मेन्द्रियमनाः

स्वस्थ इत्यभिधीयते | Su. Su.15/41 Any negative effect on Shareera has

an effect on Manas. One of the three fundamental foundations of life, along with the body and consciousness, is manas. Ayurveda places a high value on mental well-being. The main issue at hand is vishada, or depression. Acharya Sushruta refers to it as manasika vyadhi, whereas Acharya Charaka says it is one of the *Vataja nanatmaja vyadhi*.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, vishada, agni, vyadhi, manasika, shareera.

INTRODUCTION

According to *Ayurveda*, *Vishada Avastha* is a condition of extreme sadness, hopelessness, or depression that frequently results from unmet

desires, emotional turmoil, or mental imbalance. In addition to the vitiation of Manasika Bhavas like *Shoka* (grief), *Bhaya* (fear), and *Chinta* (anxiety), it is seen as a *Manasika Vikara* (mental disease) that is primarily brought on by Rajas and Tamas doshas. Ancient writings that emphasize the connection between the mind and body, such as the Charaka Samhita and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, have acknowledged the significant influence of psychological elements on general health. Along with *Yuktivyapashraya* and *Daivavyapashraya*, *Satvavajaya* is one of the three primary forms of *Chikitsa*. It operates through spiritual direction, behavioural correction, counselling, and activities that foster emotional fortitude and self-control. This subject looks at the causes, symptoms, and pathological ramifications of *Vishada Avastha* as

well as the comprehensive therapeutic function of *Satvavajaya Chikitsa* in treating it. This age-old knowledge is crucial to research and use in modern Ayurvedic treatment because of its applicability to contemporary mental health issues including anxiety and depression. Ayurveda provides *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*, a specialist treatment for such illnesses that focuses on mind control, mental balance restoration, and *sattva* (mental strength and clarity).

DISCUSSION

Kaayika lakshana	Vachika lakshana	Manasika lakshana
Anidra	Alpavak	Atichinta
Atinidra Aruchi	Ativak	Bhaya
Hritspandana Alpacheshta anaalasyata		Dukha Asthirata of manas Arati smritinasha

Samprapti of Vishada is describes as follows

Examination for vishada: Various clinical examinations have been describes in *samhitas* which includes *trividha*, *astavidha* and *dashavidha pariksha*. The relevance of psychological stress in both physical and mental health has been acknowledged by Ayurveda. The *trigunas* of *Satva*, *Rajas*, and *Tamas* appear to represent the manifestation of mental processes and consciousness. A person with *vishada* should try to increase *satva guna*, which is known as *Satvavajaya chikitsa* in *Ayurveda*, and decrease *Rajas* and *Tamoguna*. It is intended to be utilized for human mental health and is not just a type of treatment.

Dhyanam- Adhyatma Dhyana

Satyabuddhi which reduces ahamkara and this ahamkara cause disclination of different desires and wishes called “Upadha”

Vijnana- shastra jnana

Ex- Atatvabhinivesha- Friends and supporters should give true knowledge of reality.

- **Dhairya-** Strength or firmness by calming down of hyperexcited state of manas.
- **Smriti-** Trying to memorise the past incidence.
- **Samadhi-** “*Swarapu shunyam samadhi ityuchyate*”
- Avoiding *prajnaparadha*
- Supressing Dharaniya vegas
- Following **Achara rasayana**

Ahitam anupasevya hitam upasevanam

Practising Yama niyama *pranayam* and *Dhyana*. Depression is the most prevalent psychiatric condition that either directly or indirectly impacts the lives of the majority of people. With all of these corroborating references, *Satvavajaya* is a holistic, nonpharmacological treatment for depression in *Vishada*. Its use extends beyond mental illnesses to include systemic ailments, and the current study attempts to comprehend its impact on *Vishada*. Ayurveda offers a thorough system of curative treatment and primarily takes a preventative approach. Maintaining a healthy body and mind will undoubtedly be encouraged by using the numerous swasthya-varadhaka techniques in accordance with aharavihara-achara. When it comes to treating a variety of mental illnesses, Ayurveda's recommendations for the best daily and seasonal routines, nutrition, and behaviour are helpful. Ayurvedic psychology is the finest way to establish a positive and healthy mind, which helps to build sattva guna, recover from physical ailments quickly, and maintain bodily health.

CONCLUSION

Both Sharirika and Manasika Vyadhi are equally important in the modern period. Ayurveda explains Vishada/Avasaada, which is associated to depression. Depression is a major global source of illness and mortality that raises serious concerns for public health.

According to Ayurveda, there is a connection between Satva (mind) and Sharir (body). Manasika Dosha (Rajas and Tamas) gradually becomes intensified when Sharirika Dosha is disrupted; as a result, mental disease develops in addition to physical illness, and vice versa. Across the nation, depression affects people of all ages. At worst, suicidal thoughts can result

from depression. It results from the body's essential components—Tridosha, Trigunas, Rasa Dhatu, Manovaha Srotas, Satva, Gyanendriye, Karmendriye, etc.—being out of balance. A sound and optimistic attitude promotes Satva Guna.

REFERENCES

1. Charaka, Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamaji Acharya, Sutra sthana 11/45, Chaukhambha Prakashana, Varanasi, Reprint, 2010; 76.
2. Charaka, Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamaji Acharya, Sutra sthana 7/51-52, Chaukhambha Prakashana, Varanasi, Reprint, 2010; 54.
3. Charaka, Charak Samhita With Ayurveda Dipika Commentary Of Chakrapani Datta, Ed. Yadavji Trikarma Ji Acharya, Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi. Charaka samhita Sharirsthan Chapter 1 verse 99-102.
4. Charaka, Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamaji Acharya, Vimana sthana 8/40, Chaukhambha Prakashana, Varanasi, Reprint, 2010; 268.
5. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita with Nibandha Sangraha commentary by Dalhanacharya, edited by Vaidya Yadavji Trikamaji Acharya and Narayana Rama Acharya, Chikitsa sthana 24/57-58, 8th edition, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2005; 489.
6. Charaka, Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamaji Acharya, Sutra sthana 20/11, Chaukhambha Prakashana, Varanasi, Reprint, 2010; 113.
7. Charaka, Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamaji Acharya, Sutra sthana 23/26-29, Chaukhambha Prakashana, Varanasi, Reprint, 2010; 123.
8. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita with Nibandha Sangraha commentary by Dalhanacharya, edited by Vaidya Yadavji Trikamaji Acharya and Narayana Rama Acharya, Sutra sthana 1/24, 8th edition, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2005; 6.
9. Vachaspatyam, by Sri Taranatha Tarakvachaspati Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series, Varanasi, 1970; V: 4933.